

Impact of Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain Model on Achievement in Genetics among Secondary School Students in Oshimili South Local Government Area, Delta State

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain Model on achievement in genetics among secondary school students in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State. The study employed a non-randomized non-equivalent pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was all the SS class 2 biology students in the fourteen public schools in the local government area. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to select two coeducational schools for the study. Only coeducational schools with at least 30 biology students were selected for the study. This is to enable formation of at least ten groups of three students per group in the experimental group. The experimental group (N=31; Male =14; female =17) was taught genetics using the digital POE (D-POE) model while the control group (N = 38; male = 20; female = 18) were taught the same concepts using the traditional method for a period of six weeks of 80 minutes per week. A 30-item two-tier Diagnostic multiple-choice Test of Achievement in Genetics (TAG) adapted and modified from West African Examinations Council's past question papers in Biology from 2009 to 2019 was used to collect data. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be 0.75 by Kuder Richardson 21. Analysis of covariance showed that the mean scores of the groups differed significantly ($F=1, 68 = 287.395, P=.000$), thus hypothesis one was retained. Also, the t-test showed a no significant difference in mean scores due to sex ($t(1.41; df =29; P\leq .168$). Hypothesis two was rejected. This result showed that adopting the D-POE model provides the impetus for students to overcome achievement challenges in genetics across in both sexes. Further studies with larger samples for longer periods is recommended. Additional factors, such as student preferences, prior technology experience, instructional variations within the model, or teacher characteristics should be investigated to enhance generalization of the findings.

Keyword: Predict-Observe-Explain, Genetics, Technology-enhanced teaching, Achievement.

Introduction

The study of Genetics has great relevance to the life of citizens of any nation. It fosters the acquisition of knowledge of important biological concepts like genes and their place in the inheritance of traits and transmission of inheritable characters, sex determination, some diseases transmission, cure and control; mutations; food production and biotechnology; population control, crop multiplication; diversities and variations in organisms; crime control and a host of other emergent areas (Jackson et al., 2018; Claussnitzer et al., 2020; Roderick et al., 2003). No nation can grow economically and technologically if its citizens are ignorant of the implications of genetics for their life and well-being. Understanding genetics is important to the study of Medicine, Pharmacy, Biotechnology, Agricultural Science, Agricultural Engineering, and disease control. Poor knowledge of genetic principles exacerbates superstitious beliefs and misconceptions about scientific endeavors and is detrimental to important national policy acceptance and implementation (Biroli et al., 2022; Hurst, 2009). For example, refusal to key into national birth control measures geared towards population control, vaccination programmes for the prevention and control of the spread of deadly diseases, apathy to utilizing innovative principles in agriculture for greater food production, and other key national programmes (Reich, 2019; Murakami, 2014). These attitudes that result from scientific illiteracy about genetics are inimical to individual and national progress. It is also common knowledge that in Africa, many families have faced marital challenges and consequent family disruptions because of issues related to the sex of children which ignorantly the female parent has often been blamed.

In spite of the relevance of genetics to life and learning, there have been consistent reports of poor students' achievement in major examinations (West African Examinations Council chief examiner's reports) since 2009. Studies (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Haskel-Ittah & Yarden, 2018; Fasasi, 2021; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017) have shown that the situation has not changed appreciably. Poor understanding of Genetics contributes greatly to students' poor performance in biology in the senior secondary school examinations. In 2019 in particular, the WAEC Chief Examiners' report noted with displeasure that students had a poor grasp of knowledge of genetics and accused biology teachers of not teaching Genetics at all or doing so unproductively. Okebukola (2014), and Haskel-Ittah and Yarden (2018) also identified Genetics among contents in Biology

which learners find difficult because of the abstractness of the concepts and the naïve views that some teachers and students hold before instruction. Akanbi and Kolawole (2014) have expressed concern about this trend and attributed it to a number of variables, one of which is the poor teaching practices employed by biology teachers, who neglect to acknowledge the pre-existing notions or conceptions of their pupils prior to formal training. Some of the views which students bring into the science classrooms are tenacious, not in harmony with the scientific views (Misconceptions or alternative conceptions), and thus resistant to change (Ezechi, 2017, Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017). Research (Haskel-Ittah & Yarden, 2018) has shown that most teaching strategies employed by teachers neglect the methods for diagnosis of students' pre-existing conceptions (prior knowledge) and the naïve reasoning behind them which Ausubel (1968) claims are the most influential single factor affecting meaningful learning.

Misconceptions are perceptions and understandings of concepts that are peculiar to a student but which are not in conformity with the scientific views. Halim et al (2019) identifies the causes of misconceptions to be more at the stage of cognitive development and often in contexts that are linked to emotions of pleasure or displeasure. They may also be culture related or triggered at any stage of formal education. Omoifo (2012) explains that no matter the source or origin of the misconception, it is a major factor affecting students' science achievement. It is thus of immense priority for biology teachers to help learners modify their non-science views in line with scientific principles through adequate instructional procedures. This modification process is termed conceptual change and involves the elimination of pre-instructional views previously held by learners and the restructuring of existing knowledge (Nadelson, et al. 2018) oftentimes through the instructional process. Such a process of instruction must allow teachers to uncover the incorrect views of students and give opportunities for learners to modify their perceptions through active engagement with the learning process. Wandersee et al. (1994) in Chavan and Patankar (2015) suggested some conceptual change instructional strategies such as word association, concept mapping, prediction-observation-explanation (POE), computer simulations, diagnostic tree, Analogy, and rebuttal tests, among others. In a multicultural and multi-ethnic society like Nigeria, evidence of learners having difficulty navigating between indigenous beliefs, cultural differences, and school science views exist (Sumadic, 2015). For students to develop ability to effectively navigate through these impediments requires that teachers apply appropriate conceptual change models that improve teaching and consequently, improve learning and retention of learned materials (Yang & Chen, 2023). The Predict-observe-explain (POE) model provides opportunities for teachers and students to navigate science in ways that afford chance to study science more actively. With the pervasive nature of technology, its incursion into science classrooms, and the exigencies of modern societal communication emergencies, it becomes necessary to incorporate digital resources into the POE model to enhance its versatility, efficiency and acceptability by learners.

Another aspect of this study is to determine if the model is sensitive to learners' gender. This study, therefore, aims at applying a digitalized prediction-observation-exploration (D-POE) model in helping biology students learn Genetics in secondary schools. The rationale for this is to exploit the enhancing digital characteristics to attract, sustain and engage students while they as study genetics and determine the efficacy of the model in helping the students learn abstract concepts as in genetics.

Theoretical framework

Helping learners to learn difficult concepts has been one of the major focuses of instructional efforts of science teachers and science education researchers. Social constructivism put forward by Vygotsky explains the process and product of offering educational help to learners through scaffolding within the learner's zone of proximal development (ZPD). According to Vygotsky (1978), the ZPD is "the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers". Science teachers are thus scaffolds to help learners achieve learning goals, especially in difficult areas of science learning such as genetics. Therefore, instruction should target enabling learners to operate in their ZPD using the instructional scaffold available through the classroom's social interaction and networking platforms to restructure, modify or completely overcome their naïve views held over time about science concepts. Such views have been reported to be tenacious (Nadelson et al. 2018; Fasasi, 2021; Moemeke & Omoifo, 2009; Moemeke, 2009) and require deliberate instructional targeting to change. As stated by Posner et al. (1982), in their initial discourse on conceptual change, four influential conditions that facilitate conceptual change are:

1. Awareness of the shortfall in the appropriateness of a held view in solving particular problems (dissatisfaction)
2. Discovery of more plausible alternative strategies (intelligibility)
3. Proof of the reasonableness of an explanation (plausibility)
4. Applicability of the alternative explanation in the problem situation (fruitfulness)

This implies that in order to accomplish conceptual change, the learner needs to be convinced about the efficacy of the restructuring process, deliberately key into it, and apply it in learning the stipulated concepts.

Conceptual change refers to restructuring the existing knowledge that learners of science hold due to misconceptions, experiences, and intuitive thinking, resulting from everyday experiences, and previous superficial science instruction. Restructuring entails that existing knowledge and experiences (schemas) which are found not to satisfactorily explain new phenomena are modified in the light of more current and accurate new information resulting in the formation of new schemas that adequately explain them (Accommodation). However, the old schemas remain dormant or suppressed in the context but are not completely discarded as supposed by the Piagetian model of conceptual change (Nadelson et al. 2018). It means that the dormant or suppressed schema may become relevant again in a completely different context where it could be used to explain phenomena. Thus, learners could harbour a myriad of schemas and conceptions about a phenomenon simultaneously. The prediction-observation-explanation (POE) strategy is a conceptual change instructional model put forward by White and Gunstone (1992). It is an innovative approach that applies constructivist learning principles that by engaging in prediction, observation, and explaining of the observed result, students can build their knowledge, and detect and correct their misconceptions about a concept thus improving their creativity and thinking ability (Jasdilla, et al 2019). To achieve this, firstly the individual student's conception of a concept or idea and the reason/s are uncovered (Prediction). Secondly, the student carries out activities that enable the observation of the process in question (Observation), and thirdly, the student uses observed knowledge to explain phenomena and resolve or reconcile any inconsistencies between their analysis of the observation and their prediction (explanation). The information obtained from the students helps the teacher to identify existing misconceptions about the concept and on this basis, find sustainable solutions to such misconceptions. POE might thus be utilised to investigate students' concepts at the outset of a subject or to enhance understanding at the end of a teaching episode. This model focuses on examining the appropriateness of students' pre-existing ideas and attitudes and connecting them to the context. In reality, teachers often employ two activities to help learners achieve this. They are practical hands-on and problem-solving activities found most beneficial when resources are not only available but in enough supply.

In contrast, the traditional teaching method is teacher-directed and teaching is done in a way that encourages sitting, listening, and fact memorization (Tularam, 2018). In the traditional approach, the teacher engages in direct instruction with the primary intention of passing knowledge to students and conducting testing and assessment (Abah, 2020). The traditional teaching method has been under attack for the many woes of science learning by students such as the inability to think like scientists, the poor conceptualization of science concepts, poor interest and motivation to learn science, among others. This is attributable to the traditional method's neglect of learners' prior views and often fails to deliberately take into account the meaning of specific words as used and understood by classroom teachers and students. Abah (2020) however cites the productive education anchored on the rich culture and tradition of countries such as Korea, Finland, and China as evidence that the traditional method is not a total misfit as often portrayed by critics. This traditional method (lecture method) is still part of most other innovative methods in science education and is popular in most developing countries including Nigeria.

Misconceptions in Science Education Research and Related Constructs

Misconceptions are informal ideas held by students that are not in conformity with proper scientific understanding even after undergoing a process of instruction (Sanders 2003). These informal ideas are also referred to as naïve beliefs (Caramazza et al 1981), erroneous ideas (Fisher, 1985), preconceptions (Keng, 2000), pre-existing concepts (Hewson, 1992) multiple private versions of science (Mc Clelland 1984) personal models of reality (Champagne et al. 1983), alternative framework (Linn, 2008), children science (Gilbert, et al 1982) and alternative conception (Abimbola, 1988; Wandersee et al.1994; Ruhf, 2003). Alkhalifa (2006) explains that misconception may be in form of pre-conceived notions which are conceptions derived from real-world encounters, non-scientific views acquired by students from non-scientific sources, and conceptual misconceptions that occur when scientific material is presented to students in a way that does not challenge them to consider contradictions and confusion about these notions. To deal with their conflicts, students construct faulty models too weak to anchor and secure the knowledge. Other forms of misconceptions as espoused by Alkhalifa (2006) are factual misconceptions which are falsities and superstitions learned early in life that are retained unchallenged into adulthood and vernacular misconceptions which are products of wrong interpretation of scientific terms that have different meanings in scientific contexts and in daily life. Though sources of misconceptions are multifarious, Erman (2017) identified the characteristics of teaching resources, educators, learners, reference materials, and the connections among these elements as the primary reasons for the occurrence of misconceptions.

In Nigeria, Adebayo and Olufunke (2015) had earlier used two modified POE strategies (Generative instructional strategy GIS, and predict-observe-explain, POE) in a pre-test, post-test control group, quasi-experimental research design. The aim was to enhance basic science practical skills in lower primary school pupils in Ondo West Local Government Area of

Ondo State. A 30-item multiple-choice pictorial achievement test (PBSPST) was used to collect data. ANCOVA revealed better practical skills development in the activity-based instructional strategies (POE and GIS) in Basic Science learning of Basic school pupils. It is noteworthy that most of the studies on POE at the secondary and tertiary education levels were done in the area of physical and chemical sciences. The model has not been used to investigate abstract concepts in biology like genetics which the West African Examinations Council Chief Examiners' Reports over the years have repeatedly identified as problematic for students. In the domain of Genetics, students find it difficult to understand the mechanism because of the complex and abstract nature of the concepts which teachers often find difficult to explain without appropriate instructional devices (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Ukwa, 2007). Mustami (2016) blames most of the misconceptions and errors in the learning of genetics on some textbooks in use in Nigerian schools that do not elucidate the concepts to the understanding of both teachers and students.

Studies about gender in science learning present contradictions in literature but some studies report that girls show preference and a more positive attitude towards the study of Biology. There is a dearth of information on the influence of gender on the learning of genetics. Studies by Kessler et al. (2007) and Vlckova et. al. (2017) reported no difference in students' misconception of genetic concepts by gender but whether there exists a disparity in the achievement of both gender due to D-POE model is one of the objects of this study. It is also noteworthy that Nigerian schools have not fully investigated the use of the digitalized POE model (D-POE). Therefore, it is important to find out if applying the digitalized POE (D-POE) model will compensate for the lapses evident in the traditional lecture method and improve students' achievement in Genetics. The study aims to find out if there is any difference in the pre-and post-test achievement scores of students taught Genetics with traditional (Lecture) and those taught with the POE model fortified with digital resources. It also aims at finding out if achievement varies between the different genders among students taught Genetics using the POE model fortified with digital resources (D-POE) as well as determining the mean achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State.

Objectives of the study

The study aims to find out if:

1. Will compensate for the lapses evident in the traditional lecture method and improve students' achievement in Genetics.
2. There is any difference in the pre-and post-test achievement scores of students taught Genetics with traditional (Lecture) and those taught with the POE model fortified with digital resources.
3. Achievement varies between the different genders among students taught Genetics using the POE model fortified with digital resources (D-POE) as well as determining the mean achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean Achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized predict-Observe-Explain model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State
2. Is there difference in the mean post test achievement score of male and female biology student exposed to the D-POE model?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students taught genetics using the digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) and those exposed to the conventional lecture model in Delta state.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model.

Methodology

Pre-test-post-test quasi-experimental experimental design with non-randomized non- equivalent intact classes was used in the investigation. Sixty-nine (34 males and 35 females) subjects from two out of the fourteen public senior secondary schools in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State of which seven are coeducational, participated in the study. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw two coeducational schools with at least thirty biology students The schools were chosen based on certain criteria, one of which is that such a school must have at least 30 biology students in the SS 2 class

of 2022/2023 session. This is important to ensure that at least five groups consisting of an even number of students can be formed during the implementation process. Of the seven schools that met the criteria in the area under study, two schools were drawn randomly by ballot. An intact class from each school was randomly selected and assigned to a treatment group by ballot. The experimental class (N=31) was taught Genetics using the D-POE model while the control group (N = 38) was taught the same Genetic concepts using the traditional lecture method for a period of six weeks of two periods each week (total of 80 minutes per week).

1. Meaning of genetics, heredity and variation, transmission and expression of characters in organisms, some important terms used in genetics.
2. Mendel's work in genetics (1st and 2nd laws of inheritance)
3. Chromosomes, DNA structure,
4. Application/importance of genetics in sex determination, disease control, biotechnology engineering,
5. Health and emergency, control of hereditary diseases, food production, crop improvement, etc.

A written request for permission to use the schools and students for the study was sought from the school principals. One week was devoted to training the biology teacher in the experimental school on how to implement the experimental model using the researcher-provided Android devices, the laptop and the projector. The researcher-prepared lesson plans were given to the teacher in the experimental school one week before the training. Questions and observations from the teachers formed part of the discussion during the training period which took place the next week. During the training period, the researcher played a video of a prototype D-POE biology classroom process prepared by the researcher. The experimental teacher then taught a thirty-minute demonstration lesson under camera using the lesson plans prepared by the researcher and assisted by a technical support staff and a class assistant. The lesson was then critiqued by both the experimental teacher undergoing training (Self-evaluation) and the researcher. The training lasted for two hours each day for two days and the participating teachers were well remunerated. The biology teacher for the control school was given the researcher-prepared lesson plans covering the same concepts as that of the experimental group to study a week before the treatment began and was asked to teach by following the lesson plan strictly. All classes were taught by the teachers under the supervision of the researcher. The actual teaching lasted for six weeks.

Experimental treatment

The following preparations were made for the implementation of the experimental treatment (digitalized POE model).

1. The researcher provided ten Android phones with internet subscription from a WIFI, a laptop, a projector and ensured that power was readily available during the experimental lessons through a power generating set.
2. Experiments and observations are saved on all the phones before the lessons.
3. Lesson demonstrations and observation are also available to the teacher on a laptop to which the projector is connected.
4. Assignments and digital links to further expand students' information sources are also provided to the students in the android phones. Students were shared into nine groups of three students each. Only the last group has four students, giving a total of ten groups. Each group worked with one Android phone.

During the class session, the teacher projects a question for groups to predict their group negotiated right answer. They then observe the experiments/ demonstrations/ read texts from links given about the question, consider their new information and on the basis reform/ readjust/ discard their prediction and give an explanation based on their new group negotiated understanding of the concept under study. Each lesson lasted for 80 minutes.

Data was collected using a 30- item two-tier diagnostic multiple-choice Test of Achievement in Genetics (TAG) in which students were expected to give a reason for any answer chosen. The multiple-choice items were carefully selected from West African Examinations Council senior school certificate questions from 2009 to 2019 in genetics but the reasons were generated by the researcher. Each item on the test had four options lettered A to D followed by four reasons also Lettered A to D of which only one is the key while the other options are distracters. The reliability of the TAG was found to be .75 after it was administered to non-sampled students and the data subjected to Kuder Richardson formula 21. The instrument was administered by the researcher, assisted by the biology teachers in the two schools on the first week to collect pre-test data. A score of 1 was given to a chosen correct option and 3 for a correct reason. The same instrument but with the number of items shuffled was re-administered to subjects in the two group in the seventh week to collect post-test data. The resulting data were analyzed using the t-test and one way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at $P \leq 0.05$ since the subjects varied even at the pre-test.

Results

The results from the analyses are presented in the tables below

Research Question 1

What then is the mean Achievement scores of students taught genetics using Digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) model and those exposed to conventional model in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of experimental and control groups

Group	N	Pre-test Mean	Std. Deviation	Post-test Mean	Std. deviation	Mean gain
Experimental group(D-POE)	31	4.87	1.607	11.87	1.607	77.00
Control Group (Traditional)	38	2.45	1.224	5.71	2.142	3.26
Mean difference		2.42		6.16		

Source of data: Author's Field collection, 2023

Table 1 shows that the D-POE group with Mean = 4.87 and SD = 1.607 at the pre-test and 11.87 and SD=1.607 at the post-test (Mean gain =7.00) gained exceedingly from treatment compared to the control group (Pre-test Mean = 2.45; Post-test Mean =5.71; Mean gain = 3.26). To test for the significance of the difference, the data were subjected to a one-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), and the result is shown in Table 2 below.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students taught genetics using the digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain (D-POE) and those exposed to the conventional lecture model in Delta state

Table 2: ANCOVA summary for mean pre and post-achievement scores of experimental and control

Source	Type III Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	1070.731	3	356.910	204.449	.000	Sig. $P \leq .05$
Pretest(Covariate)	186.830	1	186.830	107,002	.000	
Group	1003.422	2	501.711	287.395	.000	
Error	113.472	65	1.746			
Total	5286.00	69				
Corrected total	1184.203	68				

Source of data: Author, field

Table 2 shows that there is a significant difference ($F(1, 68) = 287.395, p = .000$) in the achievement of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group (D-POE model). There is therefore a significant difference in the mean posttest achievement scores of students who were taught using the D-POE model compared to those who were taught using the traditional lecture method even at an alpha level as low as .000. Null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of those taught with D-POE and those taught with Traditional model is rejected. There is a significant difference in the achievement scores of students in the two groups.

Research Question 2

Is there difference in the mean posttest achievement score of male and female biology student exposed to the D-POE model?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of male and female experimental subjects at post-test

Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Male	14	11.42	1.74
Female	17	12.24	1.43

Table 3 shows that the mean score of female students (12.24) is slightly higher than that of males (11.42) in the experimental group. This implies that the females benefited slightly more than the males from the D-POE model. To determine the significance of this difference, the data were subjected to a t-test and the result is shown in Table 4 below.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the achievement of male and female experimental subjects

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	t	Sig. 2-tailed
Male	14	11.42	1.74	29	1.41	.168
Female	17	12.24	1.43			

$P \leq .05$

Table 4 revealed that the slight difference in the mean achievement of males (Mean = 11.42, SD= 1.74) and females (Mean = 12.24, SD =1.43) is not significant $t(1.41; df =29; P \leq .168)$ at the alpha level of 0.05 set for this study. There is therefore no significant difference in the achievement of males and females in the experimental group at post-test

Discussion of Findings

For clarity, this discussion of findings will be taken on the basis of hypotheses explored in this study. Hypothesis 1 which stated that the mean post-test achievement scores of biology students who were taught genetics using the D-POE and conventional lecture models did not differ significantly was analysed using ANCOVA. The results show a substantial difference in the mean post-test achievement scores between the experimental group (D-POE) and the control group (Traditional Lecture). The D-POE group exhibited a notably higher mean gain (7.00) compared to the control group (3.26). The ANCOVA analysis confirms a significant difference in achievement between the two groups, favouring the D-POE model ($p = .000$). Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected and contrary to the initial assumption of this study. The study investigated provides clear evidence of the impact of the D-POE instructional model on Biology students' understanding and reasoning about genetic concepts. Before this study, there are a huge body of information on students' limited understanding of genetics and their applications in nature among Nigeria secondary school students (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017; Okebukola, 2014; Mustami, 2016). Reasons advanced for the poor conceptual understanding of genetics range from misconceptions due to cultural influences, the abstractness of the concepts, the use of inappropriate instructional models while teaching the concepts, and even the dearth of appropriate instructional materials and media. Also, available research evidence points to the efficacy of different variants of the POE model on a diverse range of outcome measures (Adebayo and Olufunke, 2015; Jasdilla, et al 2019) but due to the high prevalence of teachers' use of the traditional methods, secondary school biology students are not afforded the opportunity to undertake the steps inherent in the D-POE model while learning genetics. When provided with and engaged in such crucial mental involvement in learning, students' reasoning becomes improved and learning becomes productive. The result presented here contributes and provides strong evidence about the impact of D-POE intervention on students learning of Genetics through a quasi-experimental study design. The findings indicate that the D-POE model led to significantly higher achievement compared to traditional lecture methods in the sample. This suggests that incorporating computer-enhanced POE models may be beneficial in enhancing student learning outcomes in biology, specifically in the topic of Genetics and especially in similar populations as that used in this study. This finding reiterate the influence of technology and digitization in enhancing and fostering learning among students.

Hypothesis 2 stated that the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female biology students taught genetics using the D-POE model did not differ significantly. The analysis revealed that females had a slightly higher mean post-test score than males. However, the t-test results revealed that this difference is not statistically significant ($p = .168$), suggesting that gender did not significantly impact achievement in the experimental group. It also signified that the D-POE experimental model is not gender biased nor selective. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported. Although there was a slight difference in achievement between male and female students in the experimental group, this disparity was not statistically significant. Thus, the D-POE model appears to be equally effective for both male and female students in enhancing achievement in Genetics. This is in line with Kessler et al. (2007) and Vlckova et. al. (2017) who found no difference in achievement based on gender parameters. The benefits the subjects derived from the model were not influenced by their gender and as such, achievement gains were unbiased for both genders.

Implications for Teaching: These results underscore the potential of innovative teaching methods, such as the D-POE model, in improving student learning outcomes. Science, specifically biology teachers at all levels may consider integrating technology-enhanced approaches into their Predict-Observe- Explain model of teaching practices to enhance student engagement and understanding and achievement.

Conclusion

Learning genetics has been problematic for biology students over the years. Researchers have been in search of teaching and learning models that will help students overcome the challenges of learning the concepts. These challenges have been attributed to misconceptions held by both teachers and their students, some of which are cultural, conceptual, or textbook related. The tenacity of these misconceptions and naive views have made them resistant to instructional devices that do not deliberately focus on the underlying views that the students bring to class and have often resulted in poor achievement in biology in external examinations by secondary school students. The application of the Predict-Observe-Explain model of conceptual change enhanced with computer-based learning resources has helped the learners extend their learning as well as focus on the underlying misconceptions. This resulted in the better achievement of the experimental group compared to the control (Traditional Lecture method) group. Finally, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of the D-POE model in enhancing student achievement in Genetics, with no significant gender differences observed. These findings have implications for teaching practices and warrant further exploration in educational research.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended as follows:

1. The digitalized Predict-Observe-Explain model is efficacious in helping biology students learn genetics therefore biology teachers should utilize the model for teaching Genetics and other biology concepts that students find difficult because of their abstractness.
2. Since the D-POE model is not gender discriminatory, biology teachers should utilize it in overcoming gender bias in curriculum implementation such that learners of both gender can learn side by side and maximize their potentials. Infuse technology into the teaching of biology as it improves students' participation, engagement and achievement.
3. Utilize the D-POE model to improve their students' understanding and achievement in genetics since it is not gender discriminatory.
4. Biology teachers should avoid incessant use of traditional methods of teaching biology and science in general because it does not cater for most learning challenges which students experience as they learn.
5. Government and stakeholders in education should provide digital teaching resources such as computers, android phones, generating sets, and projectors to school as well as energy so that teacher can creatively innovate in their teaching of biology.
6. Teachers should maximize the characteristic properties of technology such as collaboration, individualization of teaching and learning, greater engagement, instant feedback and interest enhancement in improving learning of biology in secondary schools in Delta state.

Acknowledgements

My thanks goes to the students and biology teachers in the two schools in Oshimili South Local Government area of Delta State used for the study. I also appreciate the principals of the two schools and the supervising unit of the Ministry of Education who approved the use of the schools. I also appreciate the authors whose intellectual properties were cited in this work.

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